

KEY INDICATORS

With 265,365 hectares, Lithuania had 9.0% of its farmland under organic management, which was above the average of the EU-13 member states (6.3%). Growth from 2001-2022 was almost fifty-fold and thus considerably higher than in the European Union. Retail sales data is not available for Lithuania.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

6,769 ha (0.3%)

265,365 ha (9.0%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

3,820%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

160,516 ha (7.1%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

4,262 ha (22.4%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

100,856 ha (15.3%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

861 MT (21.7%)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

430 (0.2%)

3,002 (1.8%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

13

Processors

N/D

162

Importers

N/D

1

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

20,959 MT

Source: FIBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

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DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN LITHUANIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Ekoagros, Eurostat, Nic Lampkin

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Lithuanian CAP strategic plan foresees a doubling in area supported (to nearly 13% of UAA) and expenditure for organic farming, with a small increase in average expenditure per hectare. In total for the 2023-2027 period, organic support is forecast to account for over a third of environmental expenditure and nearly 10% of total CAP spending. In 2019, conversion support was only slightly higher than maintenance, but the differential has been increased by up to 25% for most crops from 2023. However, arable support per hectare has been reduced from 2023 compared with 2019.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	184 kha	382 kha (+107%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	6.2%	12.8% (+107%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	77%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	36 M€	86 M€ (+138%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	197 €	226 € (+15%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P1/P2)*	403 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	753 M€	37.7%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	314 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	4,183 M€	9.6%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	182	298	525	534
	2023	P1	206	280	652	654
Change from 2019 to 2023			+13%	-6%	+24%	+22%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	176	283	525	518
	2023	P1/P2	176	273	525	518
Change from 2019 to 2023			+3%	+5%	0%	+3%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		+3%	+5%	0%	+3%
	2023		+17%	+3%	+24%	+3%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing
- P2 funding from 2023 used for training (one year only), cereals and permanent grassland

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Lithuania has had no previous action plans and is one of very few countries in the EU not yet to have produced or planned an action plan for the current period.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	None	None	None
Current Action Plan	None	None	None

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (NONE)

PRODUCTION

MARKETS

INFORMATION

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (NONE)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Lithuania is nearly 14%. Lithuania was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.